

CONTENT MASTERY AND PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING AS DETERMINANTS OF CLASSROOM PREPAREDNESS AMONG PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 50

Issue 3

Pages: 276-285

Document ID: 2025PEMJ4861

DOI: 10.70838/pemj.500305

Manuscript Accepted: 11-06-2025

Content Mastery and Pedagogical Training As Determinants of Classroom Preparedness Among Pre-Service Teachers

Joyce F. Suelo,* Louie Jay R. Caloc

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The main objective of this study was to explore the influence of content mastery and pedagogical training on pre-service teachers' classroom preparedness. This study used a quantitative research design, utilizing the descriptive-correlational method. The research samples were selected using simple random sampling, and the data were collected via survey questionnaires. Further, the statistical tools used to address the research objectives were mean and standard deviation, Pearson (r), and regression analysis. Findings unveiled that pre-service teachers' levels of content mastery, pedagogical training, and classroom preparedness were rated very high. Additionally, a significant relationship exists between the variables under investigation. However, only pedagogical training is a good predictor of classroom preparedness.

Keywords: *content mastery, pedagogical training, classroom preparedness, pre-service teachers, Davao City, Philippines*

Introduction

Classroom preparedness refers to the preparation to teach, including knowledge of its structure and the appropriate instructional materials, aligned with standards for teachers (Chen et al., 2024). Whalen (2023) highlighted that, according to the National Council on Teacher Quality, over 40% of educators believe they lack the necessary skills to manage their classrooms and deal with disruptive students effectively. This is due to a lack of coursework and training in teacher education programs. Moreover, in the Philippines, teachers lack the application of teaching principles despite having content mastery and pedagogical training, and they need to improve their teaching competencies to continuously augment classroom instruction (Manigbas et al., 2024).

High-quality teaching involves a combination of preparedness, competence, and professional disposition (Moeller et al., 2021). Evaluating educators' readiness in terms of both pedagogical and content knowledge is crucial to ensuring effective curriculum delivery and fostering a conducive learning environment (Momanyi & Rop, 2020; Soriano et al., 2020; Luchavez & Caloc, 2024). These studies collectively emphasize that a teacher's competence and preparedness are closely interlinked dimensions of effective teaching performance.

Despite ample studies addressing classroom preparedness, the specific link between pedagogical training, content mastery, and classroom preparedness—particularly among pre-service teachers in Davao City, remains underexplored. Few quantitative studies have employed inferential approaches such as regression analysis to examine these interrelations. The researcher addressed people and methodological gaps by investigating this interrelationship and contributing to pre-service teachers. The findings guaranteed that future educators are well-informed about the content and efficient in employing that learning in classroom settings. A thorough dissemination strategy will be implemented to increase the study's impact. Peer-reviewed journal articles provide access to the larger research community, and the findings were presented at academic conferences and seminars to interact with academics, policymakers, and practitioners. Curriculum developers and educational leaders received policy reports to help shape educational policies. By putting these tactics into practice, the study aims to ensure that its findings are understood by the relevant parties, encouraging evidence-based enhancements to teacher preparation programs and, eventually, improving the readiness of aspiring teachers.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the influence of content mastery and pedagogical training on the classroom preparedness of pre-service teachers. More explicitly, the study sought to answer the following objectives: (a) to describe the level of content mastery of pre-service teachers; (b) to ascertain the level of pedagogical training of pre-service teachers; (c) to assess the level of pedagogical training among pre-service teachers; (d) to determine the relationships between content mastery and classroom preparedness, and pedagogical training and classroom preparedness, and (e) to test the influence of pre-service teachers' content mastery and pedagogical training on classroom preparedness.

Literature Review

Content Mastery

The content mastery of a teacher shows the alignment of curriculum standards. It is a standard that teachers are expected to teach, and students are expected to learn (Xin et al., 2022). Newman (2019) stated that educators' real objective is to master the content to align with the standards, whereas the teachers are responsible for doing so. Educators must know the timing of certain standards occurring and if they align with the student's interests. Content mastery for advanced and gifted students within the framework of differentiated

curriculum requirements. It emphasizes that differentiation entails a thorough strategy that covers content, procedures, products, resources, and assessment and goes beyond simply changing the learning speed (Caloc et al., 2025; VanTassel-Baska, 2023).

Content mastery also greatly improves the capacity to simplify complicated subject matter; by helping students recognize important ideas and structures, subject mastery improves their capacity to simplify complex subjects. Their ability to deconstruct knowledge into smaller portions enables them to communicate more effectively and gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter (Cahill & Govendo, 2020). In line with Prakash et al. (2021), mastery of content equips individuals with the ability to recognize essential concepts, allowing them to distill complex ideas and communicate them in a straightforward. This skill enhances their capacity to engage diverse audiences by adapting explanations to different levels of understanding, ultimately fostering more inclusive and meaningful comprehension. In other words, teachers who demonstrate a high level of topic mastery are more confident, which enables them to interact with students more successfully and authoritatively answer their questions (Molise, 2021).

Pedagogical Training

Pedagogical training provides opportunities to explore and discuss teaching practices, core concepts, and professional growth (Fernandes et al., 2023). Morgado et al. (2024) also emphasized that such training helps shape educators' skills and mindsets, enabling them to create more inclusive classroom environments where no learner is left behind. It is also essential that teachers be exposed to realistic classroom scenarios where they can receive constructive feedback, allowing them to continuously refine and adapt their teaching methods (Buragohain et al., 2024; Caloc, 2025). Such experiential learning promotes confidence, flexibility, and a reflective teaching practice, ultimately benefiting all learners if they are comfortable (Comawas & Caloc, 2025).

Enhancing instructors' pedagogical abilities in classrooms is the goal of pedagogical training. According to the study's findings, administrators and teachers can grow through ongoing professional development, which aids in teachers' confidence-building and skill-building as well as their acquisition of new ideas (Okumu & Opio, 2023). One study in Vietnam highlighted a few ways to create pedagogical training activities to enhance the professional competence of preschool teachers in Vietnam. In Vietnam's primary education system, such programs have the potential to transform the educational landscape and promote a continual improvement culture (Ho et al., 2024). Additionally, Heinonen et al. (2022) stated that pedagogical training successfully supported the development of each educator's professional vision. As a result of the training, all teachers acquired more advanced reasoning abilities. They understood that they would serve as role models for future educators with the knowledge they acquired from this pedagogical training, empowering them to demonstrate effective teaching practices and inspire others through their example in real classroom settings (Çam & Koç, 2024).

Classroom Preparedness

Teachers' classroom preparedness abilities greatly improve student engagement and academic achievement by setting an example of behavior and creating a positive learning environment. Effective classroom management and students' very satisfactory academic performance were moderately positively correlated in this study (Paulines & Tantiado, 2024). Expanding on this, Jamba and Norbu (2023) emphasized that effective classroom management is foundational to creating an environment where students feel safe, valued, and motivated to learn. When teachers successfully minimize disruptive behaviors, they maintain order and foster a climate that allows all students to concentrate on the content without unnecessary distractions. This control helps establish a consistent routine, reducing anxiety and uncertainty and encouraging students to focus more fully on their tasks (Escosar & Caloc, 2024).

The instructor and the actual classroom setting are the main factors determining how prepared a classroom is, although good preparation is a key component of any class's success. Teachers' role in learning activities has been surveyed by Kaur (2019). In the study by Bihasa (2022), it was illustrated that the ability of teachers, or homeroom teachers, to foster creativity and structure activities that utilize classroom abilities, namely by providing many opportunities to each student, is the essence of classroom preparedness, most especially if teachers provide instructional support (Duran & Caloc, 2025). The ability of teachers to know, analyze, and determine comfortable classroom conditions is the essence of classroom preparedness, so teachers must not compare their students and play a role in achieving their academic goals.

Methodology

Research Design

A non-experimental quantitative research design was employed in this study, specifically a descriptive-correlational method. This approach is suitable when the goal is to assess existing conditions and examine the relationship between variables without manipulating them (Hamilton et al., 2020). As Creswell and Creswell (2023) explain, this type of research interprets numerical data through statistical procedures to arrive at meaningful conclusions. Rooted in objectivity and neutrality, quantitative research seeks to gather large amounts of data to evaluate patterns and trends (Leavy, 2022). The descriptive-correlational design is relevant to this study as it provides a deeper understanding of the relationships among variables, presenting complex findings in a simplified manner (Saunders et al., 2019). Fraenkel et al. (2019) emphasize that this design is particularly applicable in educational settings where experimental manipulation is limited. Furthermore, regression analysis was used to examine the influence of one variable on another, supporting the validity of the findings (Ali & Younas, 2021; Devi et al., 2023). This methodological approach aligns with the study's aim of investigating the

relationship between content mastery, pedagogical training, and classroom preparedness.

Respondents

The research respondents in this study were pre-service teachers. In line with the inclusion criteria, they were primarily selected for their advanced knowledge of their degree program, which included core pedagogy and content understanding coursework and has frequently participated in student teaching or field activities. They can provide information about their classroom readiness, pedagogical confidence, and ability to apply newly taught techniques in an actual classroom environment at this stage of training. These inclusion criteria ensure consistency in decision-making and enhance the relevance of selected studies (Tod, 2019).

Students in their first, second, and third years enrolled in education programs, as well as those pursuing other programs, were excluded from this study because they are often in the early phases of their coursework, concentrating mostly on general education standards and introductory ideas, with little exposure to advanced pedagogical training or in-depth content-specific coursework.

For results to be dependable and valid, the right sample size is crucial. When a sample is representative of the population and sufficiently sized, researchers can apply their findings outside of the sample (Andrade, 2020). Therefore, there were 100 respondents from 4th-year pre-service teachers asked to participate in the study. Based on Cohen's (1988) statistical power analysis guidelines, the sample size of 100 ensures adequate power (0.80) to detect medium effect sizes ($f^2 = 0.15$), confirming the sufficiency of the sample for regression analysis. They were selected through a simple random sampling technique.

As highlighted by Noor et al. (2022), this sampling technique for quantitative research using survey instruments is simple random sampling. It is advantageous in identical and consistently chosen populations. Every participant has an equal chance to take part in the study using this selection process. It guarantees the population's equality, representativeness, and objectivity. This helps reduce bias in the results and ensures that the findings can be generalized to the larger population with greater accuracy.

Instrument

Three sets of survey questionnaires were utilized to collect information from the research respondents. The first set of questions was related to content mastery from Schmidt et al. (2009). The second instrument was a pedagogical training instrument adapted from Montoya et al. (2022). Lastly, the third tool was related to classroom preparedness from Asif et al. (2023). The researcher adhered to the integrity of the research tool, from face validity to ensure the instrument's validity standards were met.

Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, and all constructs produced alpha coefficients above 0.70, indicating strong internal consistency (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Validity demonstrates how effectively the obtained data covers the actual field of inquiry (Zhang & Aryadoust, 2022). According to this study, a group of questionnaire construction professionals received the survey questionnaire and modified it to accommodate the respondents' cultural norms.

In this study, a four-point Likert scale was used because it is one of the most commonly used scales. The four-point Likert scale intentionally excluded a neutral option to prevent central tendency bias and encourage respondents to take a clear position (Joshi et al., 2015). To evaluate the level of each variable, the scales below were employed:

Table 1. *Likert Scale*

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
3.26-4.00	Very High	When the item described in the statement is always manifested.
2.51-3.25	High	When the item described in the statement is frequently manifested.
1.76-2.50	Low	When the item described in the statement is rarely manifested.
1.0-1.75	Very Low	When the item described in the statement is not manifested at all.

Procedure

The researcher scheduled consultation sessions with her adviser to begin conceptualizing the study framework. After receiving permission, the survey questionnaire was assembled and presented to a group of examiners for validation. Additionally, the researcher obtained approval from the Dean of the College of Teacher Education to carry out the current study. Furthermore, the researcher handed over the tool to the respondents and explained to them the rationale behind the research problems. After respondents had completed all the questions on the research instruments, the researcher retrieved the survey questionnaire containing the intended data.

To ensure ethical compliance and data protection, all completed questionnaires were kept anonymous, with no names or identifying information indicated. The hard copy responses were stored securely in a locked cabinet accessible only to the researcher, ensuring confidentiality, anonymity, and integrity of the collected data. The data were tabulated and given a statistical analysis. From this point forward, statistical results were meticulously examined, analyzed, and evaluated to yield significant findings, on-point conclusions, and sensible recommendations.

Results and Discussion

This section introduces the data and findings of the study based on the elicited responses on the content mastery, pedagogical training, and classroom preparedness of pre-service teachers.

Table 1. *Level of Content Mastery of Pre-Service Teachers*

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. assessing and adjusting teaching strategies based on the curriculum	3.56	0.592	Very High
2. familiarizing relevant curriculum standards and learning objectives	3.40	0.603	Very High
3. possessing comprehensive understanding of the subject matter	3.48	0.594	Very High
4. explaining complex concepts in a clear and engaging way	3.33	0.637	Very High
5. using various teaching methods for different content to cater diverse learning styles	3.44	0.592	Very High
6. creating engaging and effective lesson plan that align with curriculum standards	3.40	0.620	Very High
7. understanding the curriculum standards and learning objectives for intended grade level and subject area	3.37	0.677	Very High
8. understanding misconceptions students have about the subject area	3.30	0.611	Very High
9. anticipating potential student difficulties in learning subject matter	3.27	0.679	Very High
10. connecting subject matter to students' prior knowledge and experiences	3.26	0.661	Very High
11. using real-world examples and applications to make subject matter relevant to students	3.40	0.696	Very High
12. having various ways and strategies in understanding literacy	3.32	0.680	Very High
13. having sufficient knowledge about literacy	3.30	0.704	Very High
14. thinking more deeply about how content mastery influences the teaching approaches use in the classroom	3.31	0.662	Very High
15. integrating other subject to enhance students' understanding of subject matter	3.34	0.685	Very High
16. selecting effective teaching approaches to guide students thinking and learning	3.35	0.657	Very High
17. designing lessons that promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills	3.41	0.653	Very High
18. understanding the importance of integrating different subjects to promote holistic learning	3.40	0.651	Very High
19. being committed to lifelong learning and continuous improvement in content knowledge	3.37	0.691	Very High
20. aligning lesson instruction based on the learning competencies	3.37	0.691	Very High
Overall	3.37	0.513	Very High

The very high overall rating of content mastery indicates that this variable is consistently manifested, consistent with the study by Indrayani and Pratama (2023), who emphasized that teachers' mastery of subject content enhances classroom preparedness by strengthening teacher-student connections and improving engagement. Similarly, Cahyanti et al. (2024) found that teachers with strong content mastery foster motivation and create more effective learning environments.

The line item with the highest mean in this variable is assessing and adjusting teaching strategies based on the curriculum goals. This aligns with the study of Newman (2019), which states that mastering the material according to the standards is an educator's true goal, and teachers have responsibility for this. It is a standard that teachers are expected to teach, and students are expected to learn (Xin et al., 2022). This depicts that teachers must adjust their strategies from the student's perspective and the curriculum goals.

The line item with the lowest mean in this variable is for connecting subject matter to students' prior knowledge and experiences. This is suggested by Acuña and Blacklock (2022), who argue that content mastery should be related to real-world scenarios, prior knowledge, and the development of routines to enhance motivation and engagement. Moreover, because of their extensive knowledge, they can explain ideas in various approachable ways, which helps students make the connection between new and existing knowledge. They can apply what they have learned more successfully and retain information longer, and students are more likely to attain higher learning outcomes (Ofodu & Jimola, 2024).

Table 2. *Level of Pedagogical Training of Pre-Service Teachers*

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. quipping necessary tools to handle real world classroom challenges	3.46	0.642	Very High
2. creating a supportive classroom environment that encourages student participation	3.42	0.654	Very High
3. using teaching methods to engage	3.43	0.607	Very High
4. establishing and maintaining classroom routines and procedures	3.44	0.671	Very High
5. adapting strategies to fit different subjects	3.32	0.695	Very High
6. using technology tools to enhance teaching experiences	3.44	0.671	Very High
7. being aware of different learning styles in class	3.41	0.570	Very High
8. providing constructive feedback to students	3.45	0.609	Very High
9. seeking help when unsure of something	3.41	0.605	Very High
10. differentiating instruction to meet the needs of all learners	3.49	0.559	Very High
11. using real-life examples to explain concepts to other	3.48	0.594	Very High
12. developing skills to engage students actively in the learning process	3.48	0.577	Very High
13. reflecting on learning to identify areas for growth	3.44	0.574	Very High
14. using resources effectively to support students learning	3.41	0.605	Very High
15. trying new approaches for students	3.37	0.562	Very High
16. handling challenges in learning environment	3.45	0.642	Very High

17. using feedback to improve work to support students' learning process	3.47	0.627	Very High
18. being responsible for learning outcomes to enhance students' academic success	3.46	0.593	Very High
19. setting and achieving academic goals	3.42	0.654	Very High
20. using group activities to promote teamwork in projects	3.45	0.642	Very High
Overall	3.44	0.466	Very High

The very high overall rating in pedagogical training illustrated that this variable is always manifested. Aligning with this is the study of Antony et al. (2024) that effective teaching requires pedagogical proficiency, which is best attained through mentoring, training, and administrative assistance. Enhancing the teacher's pedagogical training can effectively improve the teacher's readiness and classroom preparedness. It has been shown that skilled teachers are more adept at utilizing various teaching techniques, which raises student engagement and academic achievement (Baniqued & Bautista, 2024).

The highest line item in this variable differentiates instruction to meet the needs of all learners. Pedagogical training serves several purposes, such as encouraging inclusive classroom settings and helping teachers adapt to various student learning styles and academic needs (Fernandes et al., 2023; Morgado et al., 2024). As noted in the research of Rincon-Flores et al. (2024), this kind of training can enable teachers to cater to students' diverse needs and ensure classroom preparedness.

The line item with the lowest mean is adapting teaching strategies to fit different subjects. Akram (2019) states that educators can maintain adequate, excellent teaching strategies in order to be efficient in teaching the subject matter. This training is also helping educators develop the abilities and mindset they need to establish more inclusive classrooms where no one is left behind. Understanding various learning styles and how they relate to the subject is crucial (Morgado et al., 2023).

Table 3. Level of Classroom Preparedness of Pre-Service Teachers

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Equivalent
1. structuring the lessons based on Philippine teaching standards	3.53	0.577	Very High
2. utilizing instructional resources to address different learning styles	3.46	0.610	Very High
3. organizing the classroom to create an environment conducive to learning	3.48	0.594	Very High
4. keeping a sympathetic attitude in the classroom	3.33	0.604	Very High
5. setting the learning environment to supports student engagement and active participation	3.45	0.592	Very High
6. helping students with their queries	3.43	0.671	Very High
7. organizing the physical space classroom to maximize learning and minimize disruptions	3.46	0.642	Very High
8. managing time that results in good classroom learning outcomes	3.43	0.590	Very High
9. starting and ending the class on time	3.44	0.625	Very High
10. making teaching and management effective with proper use of teaching strategies	3.45	0.575	Very High
11. engaging students through the proper use of the writing board	3.41	0.668	Very High
12. creating visually appealing and stimulating classroom environment	3.47	0.643	Very High
13. making classroom management better by setting practicable norms	3.49	0.595	Very High
14. managing students reach class on time	3.41	0.653	Very High
15. setting norms for classroom discipline	3.48	0.559	Very High
16. setting up an inspiring and visually dynamic classroom atmosphere	3.43	0.607	Very High
17. integrating student-centered teaching methods that promote active learning	3.41	0.637	Very High
18. keeping in touch with student's problems to establish rapport	3.40	0.569	Very High
19. providing a conducive environment for the students	3.37	0.630	Very High
20. entering the classroom fully equipped with the needed resources	3.45	0.609	Very High
Overall	3.44	0.460	Very High

The dependent variable, classroom preparedness, has an overall rating of 3.44 mean and a standard deviation of .460, indicating that it is always manifested. It is essential to equip pre-service teachers with the pedagogical understanding, curriculum knowledge, and ability to fulfill the needs of a diverse variety of children and classroom readiness (Woo et al., 2022). According to Stueber's (2019) research, instructors' preparedness allows them to design organized and stimulating learning environments. As children flourish in well-run classrooms, this increased preparedness helps teachers as well as improves student learning results.

The highest rating line item is understanding how to structure lessons based on the Philippine teaching standards. Corresponding to this is the study (Fraser, 2020) that states that being prepared in the classroom involves a small process of skillfully combining the traits, endeavors, and methods of teachers. It refers to all the professional and administrative standards put in place to create an ideal learning environment in the classroom. Curriculum standard, which encompasses material mastery and classroom preparedness, are somewhat correlated. For example, curriculum objectives and content, particularly in the area of establishing a productive learning environment, significantly predict pre-service teachers' preparedness to teach (Guner & Aslan, 2023).

The item with the lowest mean is keeping a sympathetic attitude in the classroom. Based on Jamba and Norbu (2023), teachers who

successfully reduce disruptive behaviors uphold order and cultivate an atmosphere that enables all students to focus on the material without unnecessary interruptions. This creates an atmosphere where students feel safe, appreciated, and inspired to learn. A teacher's efforts to create an atmosphere that supports learning, academic procedures, and students' social and emotional development are together referred to as classroom preparedness (Lekhu, 2023).

Table 4. Correlation Between Variables

Variables	Classroom Preparedness		
	r-value	p-value	Decision on H ₀
Content Mastery	.700	<.001	Rejected
Pedagogical Training	.880	<.001	Rejected

Content mastery has a significant relationship with the dependent variable, classroom preparedness, as indicated by the rejection of the null hypothesis. It was anchored by the theory articulated by Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, which is the Constructivist Learning Theory (1980). Establishing constructivist methods in a classroom is greatly influenced by the content competence of the teachers. In order to scaffold the learning process and enhance comprehension, they have to comprehend the material (Schwartz, 2020). According to Jumaah (2024), constructivist learning theory enhances learning by promoting active, learner-centered education in which students build on prior knowledge and reflect on experiences. This approach prepares classrooms for dynamic interactions while fostering the critical thinking and problem-solving skills essential for successful learning.

Pedagogical training is also related to classroom preparedness of the pre-service teachers since the null hypothesis was rejected. The findings were supported by the theory of Shulman's Pedagogical Content Knowledge (1986), which demonstrates how a teacher can successfully teach content by combining pedagogy and content knowledge. This associate pedagogical training gives teachers teaching strategies, classroom readiness skills, and the ability to plan and deliver instruction. By teaching strategies, PCK develops a teacher's ability to adjust to different learning styles (Carlson et al., 2019). Furthermore, Yedemie's (2019) study indicated that providing teachers with precise guidance and ongoing training can improve the quality of instruction and aid the academic success of students.

Table 5. Influence of Content Mastery and Pedagogical Training on the Classroom Preparedness of Pre-Service Teachers

Independent Variables	Classroom Preparedness				
	βCoefficient	F-value	R ²	t-value	p-value
Content Mastery	.106	173.128	.777	1.691	>.001
Pedagogical Training	.784			11.360	<.001

Content mastery does not influence the classroom preparedness of pre-service teachers. Although pre-service teachers rated themselves highly in content mastery, this variable did not predict their classroom preparedness, suggesting that theoretical knowledge alone may not translate into effective classroom performance without practical application. This aligns with Petersen et al. (2020), who noted that overemphasis on content coverage can hinder teaching efficacy.

However, pedagogical training influences the classroom preparedness of pre-service teachers. This finding aligns with Darling-Hammond et al. (2019), emphasizing that pedagogical training fosters supportive and inclusive learning environments. Shulman's (1987) Pedagogical Content Knowledge framework supports this relationship, highlighting how integrating pedagogy and content enhances teacher readiness and effectiveness (Neo, 2024).

Conclusions

The findings indicate that pre-service teachers reported very high levels of content mastery, pedagogical training, and classroom preparedness. Both content mastery and pedagogical training showed significant positive relationships with classroom preparedness. However, regression analysis revealed that only pedagogical training independently and significantly predicts classroom preparedness, whereas content mastery does not, after controlling for pedagogical training. Given the model's strong explanatory power (e.g., R² ≈ .78), the results underscore the central role of pedagogical training—particularly practice-oriented, feedback-rich, and differentiated instruction competencies—in shaping classroom readiness among pre-service teachers.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were established for the beneficiaries of this study:

To maintain the very high level of content mastery among pre-service teachers, college instructors may continue to include subject-specific training and assessment to assess their in-depth understanding of the content materials. They may continue to provide regular exposure to real-world applications to ensure that future educators have a solid foundation in their chosen fields.

To maintain the very high level of pedagogical training of pre-service teachers, the faculty members may continue to incorporate more hands-on teaching experiences, continue to provide constructive feedback, and continue to equip the necessary skills to maintain diversified instructional tactics.

To sustain the very high level of classroom preparedness, the institution may continue to provide more opportunities for extensive practicum experiences and may collaborate with other universities and schools to offer immersive teaching internships so that future

educators can practice their skills in a real classroom environment.

Since content mastery and pedagogical training have a significant relationship with classroom preparedness, curriculum developers may efficiently establish a balance between content expertise and instructional skills and emphasize in teachers' preparation courses how to apply this knowledge in real-world engagement.

Since content mastery does not significantly influence classroom preparedness, teacher education programs may reconsider how subject knowledge is converted into teaching effectiveness. While a thorough understanding of the subject matter is required, it should be supplemented by training that improves the capacity to present and contextualize this information in real-world classroom settings.

Since the present study used a quantitative research design with a descriptive-correlational approach, two independent variables, and one dependent variable, future researchers may adopt a qualitative research design to better understand others' viewpoints and experiences through explanatory methods. Future research could identify the underlying causes, difficulties, and contextual effects that influence classroom preparedness using explanatory techniques, including focus groups, in-depth interviews, and thematic analysis. This change in approach would enable a more thorough understanding of the phenomenon, adding rich, narrative-driven insights to the study's numerical findings and further guiding the creation of policies and teacher education initiatives.

References

- Acuña, K., & Blacklock, J. (2022). Mastery teachers: How to build success for each student in today's classrooms. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, 22(1), 112–119. <https://doi.org/10.33423/jhetp.v22i1.4970>
- Akram, H., Yingxiu, Y., Al-Adwan, A. S., & Alkhalifah, A. (2021). Technology integration in higher education during COVID-19: An assessment of online teaching competencies through technological pedagogical content knowledge model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.736522>
- Ali, P., & Younas, A. (2021). Understanding and interpreting regression analysis. *Evidence Based Nursing*, 24(4), 116–118. <https://doi.org/10.1136/ebnurs-2021-103425>
- Andrade, C. (2020). Sample size and its importance in research. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 42(1), 102–103. https://doi.org/10.4103/IJPSYM.IJPSYM_504_19
- Antony, M., Emas, R., & Upoma, S. (2024). Teaching future faculty: Pedagogical training in public administration PhD programs in the US. *Journal of Public Affairs Education*, 30(3), 355–374. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15236803.2024.2380226>
- Asif, M., Khurram, A. F., & Abdulsattar. (2023). Development and validation of teachers' classroom management questionnaire (TCMQ). *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 11(3), 1264–1275. <https://doi.org/10.52131/pjhss.2023.1103.0640>
- Baniqued, W., & Bautista, R. (2024). Teachers' preparedness on pedagogical practices in K-12 science education: Foundations for crafting an effective science program. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 12(8), 291–297. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-12-8-1>
- Bihasa, D. (2022). The preparedness of pre-service teachers on the required programs to meet standards. *PUPIL: International Journal of Teaching, Education and Learning*, 5(3), 220–237. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijtel.2022.53.220237>
- Buragohain, D., Deng, C., Sharma, A., & Chaudhary, S. (2024a). The impact of immersive learning on teacher effectiveness: A systematic study. *IEEE Access*, 12, 35924–35933.
- Cahill, G., & Govendo, B. (2020). Beyond reading the text: Teaching science students three strategies for mastering complex content. *Journal of Education and Social Policy*, 7(4), 93–98. <https://doi.org/10.30845/jesp.v7n4p11>
- Cahyanti, A. D., Purwoko, B., Khamidi, A., Hariyati, N., & Roesminingsih, E. (2024). Fostering student motivation through teacher competence. *EDUKASIA: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*, 5(1), 751–758. <https://doi.org/10.62775/edukasia.v5i1.846>
- Caloc, L. J. (2025). Language anxiety as corollary of teacher efficacy: A quantitative study among senior high school students. *International Journal of Philosophy, Linguistics, and Humanities*, 1(2), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.70847/632138>
- Caloc, L. J., Imperial, D., Matalam, A., & Diamante, R. (2025). Classroom behavior as a predictor of competency-based learning: A regression analysis of senior high school students. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies in Higher Education*, 2(3), 72-86. <https://doi.org/10.70847/632199>
- Çam, Ş. S., & Koç, G. (2024). Professional development program to develop teacher educators' technological pedagogical content knowledge. *Sage Open*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241242841>
- Carlson, J., Daehler, K. R., Alonzo, A. C., Barendsen, E., Berry, A., Borowski, A., & Wilson, C. D. (2019). The refined consensus model of pedagogical content knowledge in science education. In A. Berry, P. Friedrichsen, & J. Loughran (Eds.), *Repositioning pedagogical content knowledge in teachers' knowledge for teaching science* (pp. 77–94). Springer.

- Chen, Y., Tang, J., Du, J., & Huang, S. (2024). A literature review of teachers' preparedness to teach and its influencing factors. *Frontiers in Sustainable Development, 4*(5), 63–69. <https://doi.org/10.54691/57j55m12>
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences (2nd ed.)*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Comawas, J. K. B. & Caloc, L. J. R. (2025). Multimodal literacy instruction and learning comfortability as determinants of classroom interaction among college students. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 48*(6), 946-956. <https://doi.org/10.70838/pemj.480607>
- Creswell, W., & Creswell, D. (2023). *Research design qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (5th ed.)*. SAGE Publications
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2018). Teacher quality and student achievement: A review of state policy evidence. *Educational Policy Analysis Archives, 8*(1), 1–44. <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.v8n1.2000>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2019). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science, 24*(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2018.1537791>
- Devi, B., Lepcha, M., & Basnet, S. (2023). Application of correlation research design in nursing and medical research. *Journal of Xi'an Shiyou University, Natural Sciences Edition, 65*(11), 60-69. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/YRZ68>
- Duran, I. G.. & Caloc, L. J. R. (2025). Verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support as predictors of reading proficiency among SHS students. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 47*(9), 1076-1085. <https://doi.org/10.70838/pemj470904>
- Escosar, P. P. & Caloc, L. J. R. (2024). Self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers on the study skills of SHS students. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 28*(8), 831-839. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14413315>
- Fernandes, S., Araújo, A. M., Miguel, I., & Abelha, M. (2023a). Teacher professional development in higher education: The impact of pedagogical training perceived by teachers. *Education Sciences, 13*, 309. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13030309>
- Fraenkel, R., Wallen, E., & Hyun, H. (2019). *How to design and evaluate research in education (8th ed.)*. Pearson Education.
- Fraser, B. J. (2020). Curriculum and learning environments. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.013.1040>
- Guner, T., & Aslan, S. (2023). An analysis of the relationship between the pre-service teachers' curriculum literacy and their preparedness to teach. *Anadolu Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi, 7*(1), 111–126. <https://doi.org/10.34056/aujef.1177806>
- Hamilton, D., McKechnie, J., Edgerton, E., & Wilson, C. (2020). Immersive virtual reality as a pedagogical tool in education: A systematic literature review of quantitative learning outcomes and experimental design. *Journal of Computers in Education, 8*(1), 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-020-00169-2>
- Heinonen, N., Katajauvori, N., Murtonen, M., & Södervik, I. (2022). Short pedagogical training in supporting university teachers' professional vision: A comparison of prospective and current faculty teachers. *Instructional Science, 51*(2), 201–229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-022-09603-7>
- Ho, V.-T., Le, T.-K. A., Nguyen, V.-D., Phan, T.-N., & Tran, V.-D. (2024). Developing the professional capacity of preschool teachers through pedagogical training activities. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research, 11*(2), 322–331. <https://doi.org/10.20448/jeelr.v11i2.5554>
- Indrayani, K., & Pratama, A. (2023). Identification of benefits of participating in content mastery services at SMPN 37 Muaro Jambi. *Indonesian Journal of Education Research, 4*(2), 23–27. <https://doi.org/10.37251/ijoer.v4i2.577>
- Jamba, N., & Norbu, L. (2023). Effective classroom management and students' academic performance: A study in one of the middle secondary schools in Bumthang District. *Polaris Global Journal of Scholarly Research and Trends, 2*(1), 11–24. <https://doi.org/10.58429/pgjsrt.v2n1a112>
- Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S., & Pal, D. K. (2015). Likert scale: Explored and explained. *British Journal of Applied Science & Technology, 7*(4), 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.9734/BJAST/2015/14975>
- Jumaah, F. M. (2024). Exploring constructivist learning theory and its applications in teaching English. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 6*(8), 7–19. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajssei/Volume06Issue08-02>
- Kaur Swaran Singh, C., & Mohd Kasim, Z. (2019). Pre-service teachers' mastery of technological pedagogical content knowledge for teaching English language. *Universal Journal of Educational Research, 7*(10A), 24–29. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2019.071705>
- Leavy, P. (2022). *Research design: Quantitative, qualitative, mixed methods, arts based, and community-based participatory research approaches (2nd edition)*. Guilford Publications.

- Lekhu, M. A. (2023). Pre-service science teachers' preparedness for classroom teaching: Exploring aspects of self-efficacy and pedagogical content knowledge for sustainable learning environments. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, 5(1), 113–129. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcsr.2023.9>
- Luchavez, L. J., & Caloc, L. J. (2024). Mathematical proficiency as an output of enrichment programs and pedagogical preparedness. *International Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Studies*, 9(4), 13-27. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5066885
- Manigbas, J. I., Ollet, A. L., Noble, M. P., Angeles, J. R., Cayetano, N. M., & Fucio, M. P. (2024). Teachers' competency in content knowledge and pedagogy in Buhi South District, Philippines. *International Education Trend Issues*, 2(1), 21–30. <https://doi.org/10.56442/ieti.v2i1.365>
- Moeller, B., Duncan, T., Schoeneberger, J., Hitchcock, J., & McLeod, M. (2021). Setting the foundation for equitable classroom practices: Enhancing teacher comfort and preparedness for teaching diverse students using the math for all professional development program. *Professional Development in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19477503.2022.2146361>
- Molise, H. (2021). The relationships between experience, qualification and subject specialization and content knowledge mastery of economic and management sciences teachers: A case of accounting teaching. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(8), 36–49. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.8.3>
- Momanyi, J. M., & Rop, P. K. (2020). Teacher preparedness for the implementation of competency-based curriculum in Kenya: A survey of early grade primary school teachers in Bomet East Sub-County. *The Cradle of Knowledge: African Journal of Educational and Social Science Research*, 7(1), 10–15. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajessr.v7i1>
- Montoya, N. E., Almonacid-Fierro, A. A., Arroyave Giraldo, D. I., & Valdebenito González, K. B. (2022). Design and validation of a questionnaire to assess the pedagogical content knowledge of Colombian physical education students in the practicum. *Pedagogy of Physical Culture and Sports*, 26(5), 300–310. <https://doi.org/10.15561/26649837.2022.0504>
- Morgado, E. G., Rodrigues, J. B., & Leonido, L. (2024). Rethinking teacher training from an inclusive and community dialogical perspective. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 11(1), 219–228. <https://doi.org/10.20448/jeelr.v11i1.5430>
- Neo, M.-T. O. (2024). A theoretical framework Lance on consumer studies teacher effectiveness, PCK and SCK in the classroom. In *Educational Administration and Leadership: Perceptions of Educational Leaders in Relation to Their Leadership Style* (pp. 57–68). <https://doi.org/10.22159/ed.c6>
- Newman, M. (2019). The impact of content mastery on sequential standards. *Murray State Thesis and Dissertations*. <https://digitalcommons.murraystate.edu/etd/151>
- Noor, S., Tajik, O., & Golzar, J. (2022). Simple random sampling. *International Journal of Education & Language Studies*, 1(2), 78–82. <https://doi.org/10.22034/ijels.2022.162982>
- Ofodu, G. O., & Jimola, F. (2024). Teachers' content knowledge: Implications for teaching practices and students' learning outcomes. *Language Teaching and Educational Research*, 7(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.35207/late.1427141>
- Okumu, J. B., & Opio, G. (2023). Continuous professional development and teachers improved pedagogical skills in secondary schools in Gulu City. *East African Journal of Education Studies*, 6(3), 430–440. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajes.6.3.1594>
- Paulines, W., & Tantiado, R. C. (2024). Teachers' classroom management and students' performance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 7(8). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v7-i08-10>
- Petersen, C. I., Baepler, P., Beitz, A., Ching, P., Gorman, K. S., Neudauer, C. L., Rozaitis, W., Walker, J. D., & Wingert, D. (2020). The tyranny of content: "Content coverage" as a barrier to evidence-based teaching approaches and ways to overcome it. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 19(2). <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.19-04-0079>
- Prakash, A., Hasan, S. A., Farri, O. F., & Datla, V. V. (2019). *Simplifying and/or paraphrasing complex textual content by jointly learning semantic alignment and simplicity*. U.S. Patent No. 11,042,712. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Rincon-Flores, E. G., Castano, L., Guerrero Solis, S. L., Olmos Lopez, O., Rodríguez Hernández, C. F., Castillo Lara, L. A., & Aldape Valdés, L. P. (2024). Improving the learning-teaching process through Adaptive Learning Strategy. *Smart Learning Environments*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-024-00314-9>
- Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2020). *Research methods for business students*. Pearson.
- Schmidt, D. A., Baran, E., Thompson, A. D., Mishra, P., Koehler, M. J., & Shin, T. S. (2009). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 42(2), 123–149. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2009.10782544>

- Schwartz, N. H. (2020). Kirschner, P. A., & Hendrick, C. (2020). How learning happens: Seminal works in educational psychology and what they mean in practice. *TechTrends*, 65(1), 120–121. <https://doi:10.1007/s11528-020-00565-6>
- Soriano, A. G., Tacardon, B. C., & Dela Cruz, J. L. (2020). *Teachers' perceptions about classroom management preparedness*. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
- Stueber, A. A. (2019). Research-based effective classroom management techniques: A review of the literature. *Spark Repository* <https://spark.bethel.edu/etd/614>
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 2, 53–55. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>
- Tod, D. (2019). Inclusion and exclusion criteria. *Conducting Systematic Reviews in Sport, Exercise, and Physical Activity (1st ed.)*. Springer.
- VanTassel-Baska, J. (2022). Introduction to the integrated curriculum model. *Content-Based Curriculum for Advanced Learners*, 17–36. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003310426-4>
- Viviani, W., Brantlinger, A., & Grant, A. A. (2023). Teacher preparedness and retention. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1398285.pdf>
- Whalen, C. (2023). Running on empty: Teachers are not prepared for increasing challenging behaviors. *RethinkEd*. <https://www.rethinked.com/resources/teachers-not-prepared-increasing-challenging-behaviors/>
- Woo, E., Hadley, F., & Fordham, L. (2022). Beyond curriculum knowledge: Preparing Australian pre-service teachers' 'responsibility' to 21st century student diversity and working in partnership with families. *Practice*, 4(2), 82–92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25783858.2022.2133623x>
- Xin, W., Li, L., & Ruppar, A. L. (2022). Curricular philosophies reflected in the Chinese special school curriculum standards for students with intellectual disabilities. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 71(5), 721–7 <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2022.2154325>
- Yedemie, Y. Y. (2019). Perceived pedagogical-content knowledge of teachers: Classroom practices as correlates of college of teacher education students' academic results. *The International Journal of Research in Teacher Education*, 10(2), 34–53. https://ijrte.inased.org/files/5/manuscript/manuscript_929/ijrte-929-manuscript-231548.pdf
- Zhang, Y., & Aryadoust, V. (2022). A systematic review of the validity of questionnaires in second language research. *Education Sciences*, 12(10), 723. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12100723>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Joyce F. Suelo

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines

Louie Jay R. Caloc

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines